

Improved Pyramid Wavefront Sensor Reconstruction using a Physics-Informed Neural Network

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ABSTRACT

The pyramid wavefront sensor (PWFS) is well known for its sensitivity and is increasingly being adopted in many new adaptive optics (AO) systems coming online. Although highly sensitive, this sensor is also well known for its nonlinear response in the presence of large wavefront errors. Modulation techniques have been used to extend the sensor's linear range, but these techniques limit the sensitivity of the PWFS and still require real-time optical gain tracking. Deep learning has become a popular research topic for the reconstruction of the PWFS signal to overcome these limitations, and several machine learning (ML) models have demonstrated promising results in simulated and laboratory AO systems. The practical adoption of these ML models has been a slow process, however, there are limited cases that show these models performing successfully on-sky.

Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) are powerful ML models that are developed by incorporating physical domain knowledge into a model's decision-making framework. This approach is particularly useful in cases where there is a limited amount of high-quality labeled data, but there are reliable physical laws that govern the system. This embedded domain knowledge allows the model to capitalize on typical mechanistic modeling to generalize beyond the training data.

In this paper we propose a PINN framework that integrates domain knowledge into an end-to-end intelligent control system for real-time AO with a PWFS. The PINN model is trained over a range of atmospheric turbulence conditions, where it leverages the linear response of the PWFS in low atmospheric turbulence conditions to improve the model's domain adaptation. The proposed model is tested using a simulated 8m telescope, and the results are compared to traditional neural network methods used for wavefront error reconstruction.

Keywords: Machine learning, Physics informed neural network, Pyramid wavefront sensing, Nonlinear wavefront sensing

1. INTRODUCTION

The pyramid wavefront sensor (PWFS) is well known in astronomical adaptive optics (AO) for both its sensitivity and its nonlinearity[4, 7]. Optical modulation has been used to linearize the sensor's response, which increases the linear range of the sensor. This, however, comes at the price of sacrificed sensitivity[2, 1, 16, 5, 3]. Algorithms such as the Gerchberg–Saxton algorithm can be used to conventionally reconstruct the non-linear PWFS signal, but the iterative nature of these algorithms introduces a significant time delay due to the computational time needed for solution convergence (typical AO systems allocate 10s to a few 100s of μ s to compute the correction),

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which makes them unsuitable for the real time nature of an AO system[4]. The use of machine learning (ML) for non-linear PWFS signal reconstruction has been gaining popularity as it removes the need for physical modulation in many systems or can be used along side modulation to boost the PWFS's performance; many research groups have begun to explore intelligent reconstruction methods[14, 8, 2, 11, 18, 17, 13, 15]. Archinuk et al used a simple CNN to provide better reconstruction accuracy than the linear reconstructor for a simulated PWFS AO system[2]. While Landman et al successfully demonstrated on-sky reconstruction with an unmodulated PWFS using a Unet reconstructor [12]. The implementation of an ML based reconstructor enables systems to operate nonlinearly and the ML algorithms can be optimized for a real time AO operation. This software based approach has the potential to empower systems to capitalize on the sensitivity of the PWFS.

Physics informed Neural Networks are a type of ML model that incorporates physical domain knowledge into the model's loss function. This strategy takes advantage of both ML data driven solutions, and physics-based mathematical models. Not only does this approach allow the ML model to be informed by the physics of the problem, but it has additional benefits in training by narrowing the field of exploration of the model, and aiding in the prevention of model overfitting[10, 6].

In this work we devise a PINN framework for ML based PWFS reconstruction, and created a software environment that enables closed-loop training and testing of that framework with a fully simulated observatory and AO system created with OOPAO[9].

2. PINN FRAMEWORK

We created a framework for a PINN based PWFS reconstructor, pictured in Figure 1, comprised of a simple six layer Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) trained in two stages. In the first stage the CNN is trained by providing a dataset of labeled data pairs from the target simulated telescope/instrument. In the second stage the model was trained in closed-loop receiving input data from the integrated simulated telescope and instrument system, and with the physics informed loss function.

When developing a PINN, scientific knowledge is incorporated into the ML design through the inclusion of physical domain information as soft constraints in the loss function [10]. These physical constraints act as penalizing terms which restrict the space of acceptable solutions [6]. For this research we used the relative loss of the linear reconstructor as the embedded physics based information.

Figure 1. PINN framework for the reconstruction of PWFS pupil images: the model is trained in two stages, the first stage with pupil image and phase map data pairs, and the second stage in closed-loop integrated with OOPAO[9]

A simple CNN was selected to keep implementation lightweight. Six convolutional layers were used with GeLu activation, and a fully connected layer and reshaping layer were used to shape the predicted phase map output. In the first training stage the inputs to the model are the PWFS pupil image and ground truth atmospheric turbulence phase data pairs. In the second stage the ML model also received the linear reconstructor calculated phase map to for use with the physics informed loss function. PWFS pupil input data was normalized following conventional AO system data preprocessing techniques. It can be noted that the inputs and outputs of the ML model were phase which were later converted to DM commands.

The physics informed loss is defined as the sum of the relative loss of the ML predictions plus the weighted relative loss of the computed linear phase reconstruction. In Landman's et al's work, they noted using regular RMS loss while training their PWFS reconstructor ML models caused the model's predictions to disproportionately focus on larger aberrations and lower spatial frequencies, and their group presented a relative loss function as a solution to this problem[12]. We were able to replicate this phenomenon in our experiments, and used their

relative loss approach as inspiration for both the physics informed loss function, and the loss function used in the first stage of training.

The expression for the physics informed loss function developed for the second training stage is:

$$\text{PILoss} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_i (Y_{\text{true},i} - Y_{\text{pred},i})^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_i Y_{\text{true},i}^2 + \epsilon}} + \frac{1}{M} \frac{\sqrt{\sum_i (Y_{\text{true},i} - L_{\text{pred},i})^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_i L_{\text{true},i}^2 + \epsilon}}, \quad (1)$$

where Y_{true} is the ground truth atmospheric turbulence phase map and Y_{pred} is the ML predicted atmospheric turbulence phase map. L_{pred} is the linear reconstructor calculated phase map and M is a weighting parameter used to tune the weight of the physics informed term on the system. The subscript i denotes the indexing of the spatial degrees of freedom (e.g., DM actuators) within a single training sample. A very small ϵ is added to the denominator of both terms to prevent division by zero.

3. ML FOR AO SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

An ML for AO environment was developed to enable testing and training of ML algorithms with both randomly generated frames and integrated closed-loop scenarios with an OOPAO[9] simulated telescope and AO system. The environment allows the user to set up the telescope, AO system, and ML model parameters in a configuration file. Random frame training and testing is performed in two steps, data generation and ML model training and testing. An OOPAO telescope, AO system, and atmospheric turbulence distribution is defined from the configuration file, and a dataset of PWFS pupil image and true atmospheric turbulence phase screen pairs are generated using random phase screens drawn from that turbulence distribution. This dataset is then used to perform the training and testing of the ML model.

In closed-loop training and testing the ML model learning process is integrated with the data generation in a single step. In Figure 2 the integration with OOPAO is shown. The PWFS pupil image generated for the training of the system is impacted by the DM command calculated from the previous ML model predicted phase screen frame. Allowing the ML algorithm to get feedback from the simulated telescope in the training process was a key factor in implementing the PINN framework as described above.

Figure 2. ML for AO simulation environment: this environment allows for integration with OOPAO fully simulated telescope and AO system. The ML training program receives the ground truth atmospheric turbulence frames, ML reconstructor created images and Linear reconstructor created images, and updates the ML based reconstructor based on that input.

For the experiments completed in this work the fully simulated system was configured to be a telescope with $D = 8m$, and with atmospheric conditions generated for $r_0 = 15cm$. In the single conjugate AO system an unmodulated PWFS and DM were used with 20 subapertures with the wavefront sensing happens at 550 nm. The linear reconstructor matrix was generated using OOPAO’s built-in interaction matrix function using the push-pull method and using Karhunen–Loève modes.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The ML model was tested after each of the two training phases to evaluate system performance. During the first phase the model was trained on 3000 frames, and evaluated against a linear reconstructor. Training frames and testing frames were generated randomly from $r_0 = 15cm$ conditions with no temporal correlations between frames. Figure 3 shows the performance of both the CNN ML model predictions and the linear reconstructions

over the random testing frames. Performance was calculated for each point for both the ML model and linear reconstructor by computing the root mean square error (RMSE) of each reconstructed phase map using the ground truth phase screen values as the actual value. In the random frame test the CNN based reconstructor is able to match the unmodulated linear reconstructor performance for the smallest RMS wavefront error, and demonstrates increasingly better performance for larger wavefront error.

Figure 3. Performance of CNN model after the first stage of training compared to the linear reconstructor for an unmodulated PWFS. Performance RMSE calculated for CNN model and linear reconstructor using the corresponding atmospheric turbulence ground truth frame.

Figure 4 presents the performance of the ML model after the first stage of training in closed-loop testing compared to the performance of a linear reconstructor. An open-loop reconstructor was also used to calculate optimal performance, and was plotted in the figures as "near-optimal" to provide a reference of base error - note here we are subtracting the open-loop reconstructor directly from the input phase so as to get a residual that is limited by the DM fitting error providing that near-optimal signal. These closed-loop tests were performed with twin simulated telescope and AO systems which are generated with identical hardware and environmental conditions. One of the twin systems uses the trained ML model as it's reconstructor, and the other system uses the classic linear reconstructor. Figure 4 demonstrates that the ML based reconstructor is able to achieve a stable performance quickly, and continuously corrects to around 300nm. In the same atmospheric turbulence conditions the linear reconstructor system reaches a correction of just under 400nm for the initial 100 frames, but diverges over time as expected in an unmodulated system. When the linear reconstructor diverges the ML based reconstructor is able to maintain stability.

Figure 4. Closed-Loop performance after stage one training compared against unmodulated linear reconstruction

In the second stage of training the model was retrained in the closed-loop integrated environment. In this environment the ML model is driving the loop and then evaluates it performance using equation 1 which includes information from the linear reconstruction calculation for the same PWFS pupil image seen by the ML model. The model was trained with batches of 1000 frames generated with OOPAO in a closed-loop system, with the reconstruction from the previous frame acting as the DM state while the next frame was generated. Training in batches allowed the model to experience several "episodes" of the system responding to atmospheric turbulence, providing information to the model on linear reconstruction response for different random starting frames.

Figure 5. Closed-Loop performance of complete PINN model after stage two training compared against unmodulated linear reconstruction

After this second stage of training the full PINN model was tested for its performance with random frames and closed-loop scenario reconstruction. Figure 5 depicts the results of a closed-loop test of the fully trained model. The PINN model was able to achieve a correction of around 300nm and maintain stability over 500 frames with the same atmospheric turbulence conditions used for the closed-loop test shown in Figure 4, which tested the model after the first stage of training. The fully trained PINN model was able to maintain the same level of reconstruction achieved in the first stage of training, but did not achieve a statistically significant improvement in its reconstruction abilities after the second stage of training.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We designed and explored the first implementation of a PINN framework for PWFS reconstruction in a fully simulated single conjugate AO system with an unmodulated PWFS. The PINN model trained and tested here was able to successfully reconstruct randomly generated atmospheric turbulence frames, and demonstrated better performance in random frame reconstruction than the linear reconstruction algorithm as shown in Figure 3. The model was also able to achieve stable closed-loop control in simulation, and maintain that stability with the unmodulated PWFS when the linear reconstructor diverged (see Figure 4).

While our preliminary results didn't demonstrate a significant improvement over the classical methods used for ML based PWFS reconstruction with the addition of the PINN training stage, we demonstrated the framework for the first time. More work will be done to better understand if these science informed models can improve intelligent AO systems. Additional experiments are planned to include a more diverse range of training data in both the first and second stages of model training. Additionally, as machine learning models continue to improve, larger more complex architectures may become more accessible for real time applications, and these architectures with greater capacity for feature extraction could be explored in future work.

In this work we investigated a generic fully simulated 8m class telescope and AO system with a linear reconstruction matrix that was generated by OOPAO for the system. Progress has already been made in developing an OOPAO digital twin of the REVOLT instrument at NRC HAA, and will be tested using a linear reconstructor that has been verified to have good performance for the system.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are grateful to Todd Charter and Maryam Ahang from the University of Victoria for discussions and support in ML design and development. This work was partially funded by the National Research Council of Canada New Beginnings Initiative project 1015369.

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